

LOSS ESTIMATION IN PORT HARCOURT POWER DISTRIBUTION NETWORKOmorogiwa Eseosa¹ Uhunmwangho Roland²

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KEYWORDS: NTL's, TL's, PHCN, FERMIE, WATERWORKS, RIVOC AND RAINBOW**ABSTRACT**

This work studied losses (technical, administrative and non technical) in one of the injection sub stations (trans-amadi) in Port Harcourt. It consists of 33kV incoming line and two (2) by 15MVA transformers sizes distributed to four (4) outgoing feeders three (3) feeders (Fermie, Waterworks, Rivoc and Rainbow). Data collected include current readings(energy supplied on hourly basis) and collation of consumers billed units for a period of six months(Jan-July 2013). Applying the required mathematical equations, a total energy loss (TL's and NTL's) were determined for each of the feeders and was translated into monetary terms. Necessary recommendations were made towards curbing these challenges

INTRODUCTION

Stable and quality power supply is synonymous to fast growing economic development and industrialization. Nigeria power network generates, transmits and distribute to final consumers at different voltage levels. Nigeria network currently consist of seventeen power generating stations that generates at 16kV and then transmits at 132/330kV consisting of sixty four transmission lines and fifty two buses, before it is finally distributed at 33/11/0.415kV. Each voltage levels are associated with losses either from generators, transmission or distribution lines that could either be in form of technical or non-technical. Technical losses (TL's) occur as a result of components failure, power dissipation in transmission lines, transformers (resistive losses in windings and core loss), metering and control calibration measuring instruments associated to electrical equipments etc and can easily be measured and controlled provided that the power system consist of known load quantities. It also include resistive losses in the primary feeder, resistive losses in secondary network, resistive losses in service drops and losses in kWh in meters(Fourie J.E, et al 2004). Other examples of technical losses include: unbalanced loadings, poor earthing, harmonic distortion, copper and dielectric losses due to finite resistance in conductors, etc. Non-technical losses (NTL's), on the other hand, is defined as any consumed energy or service which is not billed because of a measurement equipment failure or an ill-intention and fraudulent manipulation of the said equipment (Inigo M, et al, 2011). It may be caused from electricity theft through unmetered energy and metering inconsistencies or estimated through loads and conditions which technical losses failed to account for (Tejinder S, 2009). Electricity theft serves as the major component causing NTL's in power systems and can be defined as the deliberate attempt of an individual or group of individuals sometimes with or without power producing company's staff to alter actual billing charges or either not to pay consumed charges at all through illegal connections or using faulty meters. Recent research revealed that, electricity theft (major contributor to non-technical losses) accounts for 30% to 40% of the total annual revenue accrued in Nigeria (Anumaka M.C 2012). The aim of study is to study and determine NTL's and then provide possible solutions. This will be achieved by carrying out analytic estimation of NTL's in a local power distribution system in Port Harcourt using available records from Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Distribution losses are inherent along distribution network and comprise of TL's (load and no-load losses of transformers, line losses) and NTL's due to meter tampering, metering inaccuracies and illegal connections. No-load losses are independent of transformer loading while load losses are dependent on transformer loading. According to Millard R and Emmertson M in 2009, total loss in transmission and distribution power system comprises of three components namely the **technical losses**, inherent in the physical delivery of electric energy. It includes conductor loss, transformer core loss, and potential/current coils in metering equipment, **Administrative loss** that accounts for electric energy used by the distribution utility in the proper operation of the distribution network. and the **non technical losses**, caused primarily by

human error, whether intentional or not. Non-technical losses include the electric energy lost due to pilferage, tampering of meters, and erroneous meter reading and/or billing. All estimates of non technical losses are based on the accuracy of the calculation of technical losses (World Bank Group, 2009). Though this study is focus on non technical losses but the technical losses have to be analyzed as the non technical losses are the result of the subtractions of the technical losses from the distribution network losses. Al-mahroqi Y et al (2012) stated that TL's are part of the electric losses in the system, resulting in: losses in drivers, corona effect, iron of the transformers, eddy currents, connectors, and ohmic losses. According to Navani J.P., et al in 2011, TL's consist mainly of power dissipation in electrical system component such as transmission lines, power transformer, and measurement system etc. According to Sayyed M.B et al in 2012, this part of losses depends on technical specification of equipment in power distribution system. In a system with appropriate operating condition, most losses in the system are caused by technical losses. Reduction of these losses is difficult and almost impractical. No load losses occur from the energy required to retain the continuously varying magnetic flux in the core and it invariant with load on the transformer and load losses mainly arises from resistance losses in the conducting material of the winding and it varies with loading (Al-mahroqi Y., 2012). Optimization of technical losses in electricity transmission and distribution grids is an engineering issue, involving classic tools of power system planning and modeling (World Bank group, 2009). Information technology and data acquisition techniques have made the calculation and verification easier. With the technical information of the electricity generators and the loads, expected technical losses in the power system can be determined using load-flow analysis software(s) such as ETAP, Power World Simulator(PWS), PSCAD, MATLAB etc. According to Inigo M. in 2011, NTL's is defined as any consumed energy or service which is not billed because of measurement equipment failure or ill-intentioned and fraudulent manipulation of equipment. NTL's are more difficult to measure because these losses are often unaccounted for by system operators and thus have no recorded information (Navani J.P et al, 2011). NTL's on the other hand, occur as a result of theft, metering inaccuracies and unmetered energy. Millard R and Emmertson M (2009) stated that NTL's technical loss is the residual loss after subtracting both administrative and technical losses from the total distribution network losses.

$$\text{i.e. } NTL = E_L - T_L - A_L \quad (1)$$

Where: *NTL's* = non technical losses; *E_L* = distribution losses; *T_L* = Technical Los; *A_L* = administrative loss. The estimation of NTL's requires accurate computation of TL's and administrative losses. There are wide ranges of situations creating NTL's. A classic case is electricity theft through illegal connections to the grid or tampering of consumption meter, unmetered consumption by utility customers not accurately metered etc. In all these cases, some level of poor management of the utility in execution of its operations is present (World Bank group, 2009). According to Navani J.P et al, 2011; Millard & Emmertson, 2009; World Bank Group, 2009; Fourie J & Calmeyer J, 2004; Al-mahroqi Y et al, 2012 and Sayyed M, 2012, the most probable causes of NTL's include: meter tampering to ensure that meter records lower consumption readings, errors in TL's computation, Tapping (illegal connection) on LT's lines, Arranging false readings by bribing meter readers (i.e. utility companies staff), Stealing by bypassing the meter, Ignoring unpaid bills by utility companies, Faulty energy meters or un-metered supply, Errors and delay in meter readings and billing, Non-payment by customers. According to world bank group in 2009, NTL's in the power sector are almost non-existent or negligibly small in developed countries, as most of the population can afford to pay tariff reflecting costs of supply. Many electricity utilities in developing countries succeeded in significantly reducing or eliminating non technical losses in electricity supply on a sustainable manner but others continue to show high losses. The level of NTL's varies generally according to the economic condition of the country. Countries where GDP per capital is very low it is common to find higher levels of NTL's. However, in countries such as Indonesia and Thailand, GDP per capital is low but the reported NTL's level is remarkably low (Millard R & Emmertson M, 2009). High rates of NTL's activities have been reported in developing countries like Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, Lebanon etc where 20% to 30% of NTL's have been observed (world bank group, 2009) while Nigeria has been reported to have a large proportion of transmission and distribution losses of about 40% (Omorogiuwa E. and Ogujor 2012; Anumaka M.C, 2012). According to world bank group in 2009, in all successful cases of reduction of NTL's in developing countries, a large share of NTL's was concentrated

in users inability to pay for cost reflective tariff.. Table 1.0 shows relationship of various countries estimated power losses based on total power generated

TABLE2.1 RELATIONSHIP OF DISTRIBUTION LOSSES TO ECONOMIC PROSPERITY

COUNTRY	ESTIMATED LOSSES IN 2007	PPP PER CAPITAL 2010
Nigeria	40%	2100
India	NTL-20% to 40%	2700
Philippines	NTL-3,5%	3300
Indonesia	NTL-unknown	3400
Jordon	NTL-3% to 5%	4700
Jamaica	NTL-13,2%	4800
China	NTL-10%	5300
Thailand	NTL-0,31%	8000
Brazil	0,5% to 25%	9370
Turkey	NTL-6% to 64%	9400

METHODOLOGY

This section shows the mathematical steps, formulation and numerical analysis carried out to determine and estimate distribution losses (NTL’s) in the distribution network. It involves review of literatures relevant to the study, collection of energy supplied readings data on hourly basis from Trans-amadi injection substation situated in Port Harcourt (PH), collation of consumer/billed unit, determination of total energy losses and finally evaluating both TL’s and NTL’s in distribution network.

Data Acquisition

Data were taken from a 33/11kV substation, trans-amadi injection substation. The injection substation consists of 33kV incoming line and two step down transformer, T1 (15MVA) & T2 (15MVA) which step down 33kV incoming voltage to 11kV and distributed to four outgoing 11kV feeders namely: Fermie, Waterworks, Rivoc and Rainbow. The four outgoing 11kV feeders were considered for the analysis of NTL’s. Load current readings from PHCN log book for each of the four feeders were taken on hourly basis for a period of 6 months. Also the total number of transformers, their respective ratings and expected losses were also obtained. Load currents on each feeder were given in 3-phase i.e. (Red[R], Yellow[Y], Blue [B]) and the average current obtained represents the current for that hour and the total load current I_T is the arithmetic sum of the hourly load current for the day. Figure 1.0 shows single line diagram of the trans-amadi 33/11kV injection substation

Figure1.0 Single line diagram of the trans-amandi 33/11kV injection substation

The voltage on each feeder is 11kV, in order to calculate the energy supplied, the power formula for a 3phase system is used:

$$P_s = \sqrt{3}I_T V \cos \phi \tag{2}$$

Where: P_s = Power supply, I_T ($\frac{\text{ampere}}{\text{hour}}$) = Total load current; V =

Voltage on the line(11kV); $\cos \phi$ = power factor(0.85). The total energy supplied for the month is calculated by taking average of the respective daily energy readings. Table 2.0 shows total energy supplied for the four feeders (Fermie, Waterworks, Rivoc and Rainbow) in kwh for the period of six months (Jan - June 2013) while the total energy consumed/billed E_B for the same period is shown table 3.0. The energy billed as obtained from PHCN for the period include combination of domestic, commercials and industrial consumers on the four 11kV going feeders.

Table 2.0 Total Energy supplied, E_s for the period of 6 month

MONTH	FERMIE total unit(kWh)	WATERWORKS total unit(kWh)	RIVOC total unit(kWh)	RAINBOW total unit(kWh)
JANUARY	1,104,946.51	351,554.00	1,210,519.57	1,632,131.75
FEBRUARY	1,360,352.69	456,398.33	1,485,731.88	1,726,643.86
MARCH	1,477,189.28	468,107.09	1,695,756.79	1,594,398.15
APRIL	1,590,106.56	504,561.32	1,717,645.67	2,056,000.48
MAY	1,460,839.89	457,043.70	1,829,162.39	2,101,089.63
JUNE	1,313,073.76	479,580.18	1,892,837.66	1,816,987.51

Table 3.0 Total energy consumed/billed E_B for the period of 6 month

MONTH	FERMIE Unit billed(kWh)	WATERWORKS Unit billed (kWh)	RIVOC Unit billed(kWh)	RAINBOW Unit billed(kWh)
JANUARY	725,950.00	249,252.00	771,101.00	1,039,668.00
FEBRUARY	899,193.00	325,412.00	958,297.00	1,080,879.00
MARCH	988,240.00	338,910.00	1,064,935.00	1,007,750.00
APRIL	1,095,583.00	370,853.00	1,142,234.00	1,334,344.00
MAY	971,459.00	336,841.00	1,192,614.00	1,380,416.00
JUNE	861,376.00	346,257.00	1,194,381.00	1,153,787.00

DETERMINATION OF DISTRIBUTION LOSSES

The overall distribution losses in the system can be evaluated by comparing the results of the energy delivered by the injection substation and the total energy billed during the stipulated period of time. Mathematically; Let E_S be the overall energy delivered from the injection substation for the month, E_B be the energy billed for the month, E_L be Energy expended due to distribution losses;

Then

$$E_L = E_S - E_B \tag{3.0}$$

Using the data obtained from PHCN and applying equation 3.0, tables 4.0(a-f) is obtained for each of the distribution feeders. This table contains energy supplied, billed/supplied energy and their associated line losses for the various months (Jan-June 2013).

Table 4.0a Distribution losses on the feeders for January

FEEDER	E_S (kWh)	E_B (kWh)	$E_L = E_S - E_B$ (kWh)	$E_L\%$
FERMIE	1,104,946.51	725,950.00	378,996.51	34.3
WATERWORKS	351,554.00	249,252.00	102,302.00	29.1
RIVOC	1,210,519.57	771,101.00	439,418.57	36.3
RAINBOW	1,632,131.75	1,039,668.00	592,463.75	36.3

Table 4.0b Distribution losses on the feeders for February

FEEDER	E_S (kWh)	E_B (kWh)	$E_L = E_S - E_B$ (kWh)	$E_L\%$
FERMIE	1,360,352.69	899,193.00	461,159.69	33.9
WATERWORKS	456,398.33	325,412.00	130,986.33	28.7
RIVOC	1,485,731.88	958,297.00	527,434.88	35.5
RAINBOW	1,726,643.86	1,080,879.00	645,764.86	37.4

Table 4.0c Distribution losses on the feeders for March

FEEDER	E_S (kWh)	E_B (kWh)	$E_L = E_S - E_B$ (kWh)	$E_L\%$
FERMIE	1,477,189.28	988,240.00	488,949.28	33.1
WATERWORKS	468,107.09	338,910.00	129,197.09	27.6
RIVOC	1,695,756.79	1,064,935.00	630,821.79	37.2
RAINBOW	1,594,398.15	1,007,660.00	586,738.15	36.8

Table 4.0d Distribution losses on the feeders for April

FEEDER	E _s (kWh)	E _B (kWh)	E _L = E _s - E _B (kWh)	E _L %
FERMIE	1,590,106.56	1,095,583.00	494,523.56	31.1
WATERWORKS	504,561.32	370,853.00	133,708.32	26.5
RIVOC	1,717,645.67	1,142,234.00	575,411.67	33.5
RAINBOW	2,056,000.48	1,334,344.00	721,656.48	35.1

Table 4.0e Distribution losses on the feeders for May

FEEDER	E _s (kWh)	E _B (kWh)	E _L = E _s - E _B (kWh)	E _L %
FERMIE	1,460,839.89	971,459.00	489,380.89	33.5
WATERWORKS	457,043.70	336,841.00	120,202.70	26.3
RIVOC	1,829,162.39	1,192,614.00	636,548.39	34.8
RAINBOW	2,101,089.63	1,380,416.00	720,673.63	34.3

Table 4.0 f Distribution losses on the feeders for June

FEEDER	E _s (kWh)	E _B (kWh)	E _L = E _s - E _B (kWh)	E _L %
FERMIE	1,313,073.76	861,377.00	451,696.76	34.4
WATERWORKS	479,580.18	346,257.00	133,323.18	27.8
RIVOC	1,892,837.66	1,194,381.00	698,456.66	36.9
RAINBOW	1,816,987.51	1,153,787.00	663,200.51	36.5

ESTIMATING TL'S

TL's in distribution systems consist of both transformers (load loss and no load loss) and line losses. The line losses was analyzed using the following parameters: span-length of each feeder lines from the injection substation and characteristic impedance per unit length of the feeders. Assuming negligible line losses in distribution lines, our primary focus was to obtain data containing the number of transformers and their ratings in the areas and the .The load and no load losses for each of the transformers are computed using equations 4.0 and 5.0 respectively and the various parameters are defined. Let T_{LL} = Total load losses; LL = Expected load loss for each transformer; T_L = Technical losses; tn = number of recorded hours for each month; Tn = number of transformers serving the area.

$$T_{LL} = LL \times tn \tag{4.0}$$

$$T_L = T_{LL} \times Tn \tag{5.0}$$

Table 5.0 Estimated T_L, for the period of 6 month

MONTH	FERMIE (kWh)	WATERWORKS (kWh)	RIVOC (kWh)	RAINBOW (kWh)
JANUARY	29,177.12	3,332.25	31,762.08	36,903.81
FEBRUARY	32,322.37	3,736.72	33,866.40	41,138.64
MARCH	33,727.68	3,862.32	32,682.72	39,189.27
APRIL	34,263.04	4,207.73	36,102.24	37,710.44
MAY	30,716.29	4,385.67	35,050.08	34,080.54
JUNE	25,095.01	4,427.54	35,576.16	33,407.76

From the results obtained from the enlisted analyses, non-technical losses (NTL) are evaluated for each month by comparing the values obtained from the monthly distribution losses and the estimated technical losses. Let T_L be the estimated technical losses based on expected values from each transformer linked to a feeder.

Mathematically;

$$NTL(kWh) = E_L - T_L$$

(6.0)

Table 6.0a Estimated NTL on the feeders for January

FEEDER	E _L (kWh)	T _L (kWh)	NTL = E _L - T _L (kWh)	~ NTL%
FERMIE	378,996.51	29,177.12	349,819.39	31.7
WATERWORKS	102,302.00	3,332.25	98,969.75	28.2
RIVOC	439,418.57	31,762.08	407,656.49	33.7
RAINBOW	592,463.75	36,903.81	555,559.94	34.0

Table 6.0b Estimated NTL on the feeders for February

FEEDER	E _L (kWh)	T _L (kWh)	NTL = E _L - T _L (kWh)	~ NTL%
FERMIE	461,159.69	32,322.37	428,837.32	31.5
WATERWORKS	130,986.33	3,736.72	127,249.61	27.9
RIVOC	527,434.88	33,866.40	493,568.48	33.2
RAINBOW	645,764.86	41,138.64	604,626.22	35.0

Table 6.0c Estimated NTL on the feeders for the month March

FEEDER	E _L (kWh)	T _L (kWh)	NTL = E _L - T _L (kWh)	~ NTL%
FERMIE	488,949.28	33,727.68	455,221.60	30.8
WATERWORKS	129,197.09	3,862.32	125,334.77	26.8
RIVOC	630,821.79	32,682.72	598,139.07	35.3
RAINBOW	586,738.15	39,189.27	547,548.88	34.4

Table 6.0d Estimated NTL on the feeders for April

FEEDER	E _L (kWh)	T _L (kWh)	NTL = E _L - T _L (kWh)	~ NTL%
FERMIE	494,523.56	34,263.04	460,260.52	28.9
WATERWORKS	133,708.32	4,207.73	129,500.59	25.7
RIVOC	575,411.67	36,102.24	539,309.43	31.4
RAINBOW	721,656.48	37,710.44	683,946.04	33.3

Table 6.0e Estimated NTL on the feeders for May

FEEDER	E _L (kWh)	T _L (kWh)	NTL = E _L - T _L (kWh)	~ NTL%
FERMIE	489,380.89	30,716.29	458,664.60	31.4
WATERWORKS	120,202.70	4,385.67	115,817.03	25.3
RIVOC	636,548.39	35,050.08	601,498.31	32.9
RAINBOW	720,673.63	34,080.54	686,593.09	32.7

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Table 6.0f Estimated NTL on the feeders for June

FEEDER	E _L (kWh)	T _L (kWh)	NTL = E _L - T _L (kWh)	~ NTL%
FERMIE	451,696.76	25,095.01	426,601.75	32.5
WATERWORKS	133,323.18	4427.54	128,895.64	26.9
RIVOC	698,456.66	35,576.16	662,880.50	35.0
RAINBOW	663,200.51	33,407.76	629,792.75	34.7

RESULTS & ANALYSIS

The collected data after analysis yielded the following results shown in table 7.0(a-f), these contains the total energy supplied E_s, monthly and the estimated distribution losses E_L, and NTL's, for a period of 6 month.

Table 7.0a Results of energy supplied, distribution losses and NTL for Jan

FEEDER	E _s (kWh)	E _L (kWh)	E _L %	~ NTL (kWh)	NTL%
FERMIE	1,104,946.51	378,996.51	34.3	349,819.39	31.7
WATERWORKS	351,554.00	102,302.00	29.1	98,969.75	28.2
RIVOC	1,210,519.57	439,418.57	36.3	407,656.49	33.7
RAINBOW	1,632,131.75	592,463.75	36.3	555,559.94	34.0

Table 7.0b Results of energy supplied, distribution losses and NTL for Feb

FEEDER	E _s (kWh)	E _L (kWh)	E _L %	~ NTL (kWh)	NTL%
FERMIE	1,360,352.69	461,159.69	33.9	428,837.32	31.5
WATERWORKS	456,398.33	130,986.33	28.7	127,249.61	27.9
RIVOC	1,485,731.88	527,434.88	35.5	493,568.48	33.2

Table 7.0c Results of energy supplied, distribution losses and NTL for March

FEEDER	E _s (kWh)	E _L (kWh)	E _L %	~ NTL (kWh)	NTL%
FERMIE	1,477,189.28	488,949.28	33.1	455,221.60	30.8
WATERWORKS	468,107.09	129,197.09	27.6	125,334.77	26.8
RIVOC	1,695,756.79	630,821.79	37.2	598,139.07	35.3
RAINBOW	1,594,398.15	586,738.15	36.8	547,548.88	34.4

Table 7.0d Results of energy supplied, distribution losses and NTL for April

FEEDER	E _s (kWh)	E _L (kWh)	E _L %	~ NTL (kWh)	NTL%
FERMIE	1,590,106.56	494,523.56	31.1	460,260.52	28.9
WATERWORKS	504,561.32	133,708.32	26.5	129,500.59	25.7
RIVOC	1,717,645.67	575,411.67	33.5	539,309.43	31.4
RAINBOW	2,056,000.48	721,656.48	35.1	683,946.04	33.3

Table 7.0e Results of energy supplied, distribution losses and NTL for May

FEEDER	Es (kWh)	EL (kWh)	EL% (kWh)	~ NTL	NTL%
FERMIE	1,460,839.89	489,380.89	33.5	458,664.60	31.4
WATERWORKS	457,043.70	120,202.70	26.3	115,817.03	25.3
RIVOC	1,829,162.39	636,548.39	34.8	601,498.31	32.9
RAINBOW	2,101,089.63	720,673.63	34.3	686,593.09	32.7

Table 7.0f Results of energy supplied, distribution losses and NTL for June

FEEDER	Es (kWh)	EL (kWh)	EL% (kWh)	~ NTL	NTL%
FERMIE	1,313,073.76	451,696.76	34.4	426,601.75	32.5
WATERWORKS	479,580.18	133,323.18	27.8	128,895.64	26.9
RIVOC	1,892,837.66	698,456.66	36.9	662,880.50	35.0
RAINBOW	1,816,987.51	663,200.51	36.5	629,792.75	34.7

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

From these results, it shows, that feeders with more of domestic and industrial consumers such as Rivoc and Rainbow showed large proportion of distribution losses (34% - 35%) while feeders such as Waterworks < 27% and Fermie 32% - 34% with lesser domestic and more industrial consumers show a lower distribution losses. The research also showed that distribution losses (31.1%) are lower in the month with higher energy supply and higher (34.4%) in month with lower energy supplied for Fermie feeder and applicable also to other feeders. Moreso, the losses were computed in monetary terms done annually. PHCN charge the sum of N12.82k for 1kWh and assuming that this for all loads (commercial, industrial and residential), multiplying this amount with the distribution loss estimated would yield the total revenue supposedly lost to distribution losses and NTL's for the period of 6 month estimated. Let the total revenue loosed be R_L

$$R_L = 12.82 \sum E_L \text{ (naira)} \tag{8.0}$$

Upon application of equation 8.0 into the obtained data for the three feeders, total loss values (TL'S and NTL's) were computed and shown in tables 8.0 and 9.0 respectively.

Table 8.0 Revenue Lost in Distribution network for 6 month

MONTH	$\sum E_L$ (kWh)	$R_L = 12.82 \sum E_L$ (NAIRA)
FERMIE	2,764,706.69	35,443,539.77
WATERWORKS	749,719.62	9,611,405.53
RIVOC	3,508,091.96	44,973,738.93
RAINBOW	3,930,497.38	50,388,976.42
Total	10,953,015.65	140,417,660.65

Table 9.0 revenue lost to NTL's for 6 month

MONTH	\sum NTL(kWh)	$R_L = 12.82 \sum E_L$ (NAIRA)
FERMIE	2,579,405.18	33,067,974.41
WATERWORKS	725,767.39	9,304,337.94
RIVOC	3,303,052.28	42,345,130.23
RAINBOW	3,708,066.92	47,537,417.91
Total	9,316,291.77	132,254,860.50

VENUE: FRANCIS IDIBIYE HALL, FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, AKURE, ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

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It can be seen from table 8.0 and 9.0 that a very large amount of N140, 417,660.60 is lost over the period of 6 month as TL's and NTL's amounted to N132,254,860.50

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Research so far as shown that NTL's pose greater part of total losses in power system and majority of these are as a result of electricity pilferage. Reduction of NTL's requires regular monitoring, innovation and persistence. Six months analysis for Trans Amadi injection substation has shown that the cost of these losses (both distribution and NTL's) ranges between 26-37% of the total billed estimates of total energy delivered. NTL's have significant effect on the revenue collected each month by power utility company. If uncontrolled can bring huge financial losses. These losses are mostly accounted for by illegal connections, meter tampering, and errors due to record-keeping and metering inaccuracies such as equipment malfunction. This appalling state will continue to suffice if strict measures are not put in place. The effect of illegal connection can result in transformer overloading and life-span reduction. Rivers State Government should play a major role in combating this trend as it can bring a total collapse in the power sector due to revenue loss. The Government should not turn blind eye on these losses and must role out structures to reduce these losses to its barest minimum to lure huge private investors into the power industries and increase profit.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations to curb this power challenge include: fine and imprisonment, effective monitoring system, Implementation of Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI), Public Enlightenment etc.

Fines and Imprisonment: - There should be strict punitive laws to enforce those perpetrators caught in such illicit act to pay compulsory fines or face jail term.

Effective Monitoring System: - Routine monitoring teams should be setup to inspect each household and commercialized building for any form of illegal connections or meter tampering and to notify relevant personnel in PHCN of such acts.

Implementation of Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI):- Advanced Metering Infrastructure is the means of providing effective data acquisition procedures, remote metering and monitoring of electricity consumption by using the best available technology. Since most NTL's losses are attributed to analog meters, full implementation of pre-paid energy meters will reduce drastically problems accounted for by these losses and as such give no room of any fictitious activities being committed by fraudulent customers.

Public Enlightenment: - The public should be aware of the adverse effects of illegal connections or meter tampering and should be brought to their understanding the dangers NTL's pose to the economy and power sector.

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